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SEM Approach to Explore Technology Acceptance Decision and Behavioral Intention to Use of Information Technology (IT) Innovation Services in Educational Institutions: A Comparative Study between Two Districts in Bangladesh

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Abstract: The aim of this empirical study is to assess and compare the perception of teachers towards acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in educational institutions. **Methods:** The present study followed the UTAUT model and based on the model constructs questionnaires were designed to predict the degree of acceptance. A survey instrument was administered to participants in both Barishal (250) and Patuakhali (200) in Barishal division. The obtained information was analyzed using the statistical software package SPSS version 22.0. This study tested the model using structural equation modeling using AMOS-23. **Results:** The propensity to act showed that positive mediating effect between behavioral intention and use behavior. Seven predictors of the model yielded 89% of the total variance explained in the final measured behavioral intention to use of IT by teachers. Both samples have a favorable perception of behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in education institutions 85.6% and 85.4% respectively, and only a small percentage has negative intention to use of IT innovation services in their jobs 4.57% and 5.8% respectively. Based on the statistical outcome of study area it is interestingly noted that actual difference between Barishal and Patuakhali districts education institutions teachers' negative behavioral intention is a very few percentage (Appr. 1.23%) among the teachers. **Conclusion:** The result indicates that the improvement of IT innovation services is required in the educational institutions.

Directorate of Education general interventions should focus on promoting IT innovation among teacher's professionals. Finally, this paper introduces important methodological guidelines for measuring perceptions of behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services that currently do not exist. **Limitations:** The number of male and female teachers is not equal and our respondents were mostly men compared to women. **Practical implications:** This study extends to knowledge on IT innovation services research by using UTAUT models in the context of technology acceptance. The TADU model is a useful tool for policy makers to assess the likelihood of success for new technology introductions and the possibility of actual use. It helps the education planner to understand the driver of technology acceptance and allows them to design interventions for teachers to use of IT innovation services. **Originality/value:** This study is one of the first to utilize and revised the UTAUT model to the technology acceptance in order to develop a more robust model. It improves the model by identify new variable and adding propensity to act as a mediator that is able to measure the effect of other factors on the relationship between behavioral intention and usage behaviors.

Keywords: Behavioral intention, Education institution, IT innovation, Technology acceptance, UTAUT model.

1. Introduction

Bangladesh has emerged as an independent and sovereign country in 1971. It is one of the largest deltas in the world with a total area of 147,570 sq. km. Bangladesh has a population of about 158.90 million making it one of the densely populated countries in the world reported by the Population and Housing Census (2015). Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2011) reveals that Education in Bangladesh is overseen by Bangladesh's Ministry of Education. Ministry of Primary and Mass Education are responsible for implementing the policy for education at a local level. The highest allocation in the national budget for education exposes that Government of Bangladesh is very much keen for human resources and development through education.

According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Educational Information and Statistical (BANBEIS) survey in 2015 indicates the participation rate, enrolment rate, completion rate, and dropout rate and sex distribution of teachers. So, it is very important to compare girls and boys in different grades to understand the actual reason in the forward instead. Bangladesh has one of the lowest literacy rates in Asia, estimated at 66.5% for males and 63.1% for females in 2015. Citing the statistics from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2017) the previous rate was 72.3 percent. Bangladesh has achieved the literacy rate of 72.9 due to the active involvement of the present government said by Primary and Mass Education Minister Mostafizur Rahman Fizar in 2018. Recently the literacy rate of Bangladesh has improved as it stands due to the

modernization of schools and allocation funds for IT innovation services (bdnews24.16-June, 2018).

A study by Salim (2004) highlighted that ICT has been developing very rapidly in order to balance the whole educational system should be reformed and ICT should be integrated into educational activities. Summary of the Education Ministry Report (Ref No: 070035) in February 2009, indicated that many teachers are reluctant to use ICTs, especially computers and the internet. Some of the reasons for this reluctance include poor software design, skepticism about the effectiveness of computers in improving learning outcomes, lack of administrative support, increased time and effort needed to learn the technology and how to use it for teaching.

1.1 Research Objectives

This empirical study aims at assessing and comparing the teacher's perceptions towards acceptance and behavioral intention to use of Information Technology (IT) between Barishal and Patuakhali district's education institutions. Consequently, the following questions have been identified to help to achieve this aim. The specific research questions are the following:

- *How do the predictors of UTAUT Model influence on the acceptance and behavioral intention to use of Information Technology (IT) in Education Institutions in two districts of Barishal Division?*
- *Does there exist a difference between variables of IT innovation services of two District's (Barishal and Patuakhali) education intuitions to accept and behavioral intention to use of Information Technology?*

Across the world, many governments are now using IT innovation services to provide their citizens with more convenient access to information and services. Barishal and Patuakhali were selected for the comparison taking into consideration their common tradition of the geographic area of the southern part which makes them culturally similar. On the other side, the comparison was considered interesting since the models implemented in each district are very different. This research is grounded in a UTAUT model to determine and assess the perception of teacher's behavioral intention to use of information technology innovation services in educational institutions. The UTAUT model was chosen as the base theoretical model for this study because of its comprehensiveness and high explanatory power in comparison to other technology acceptance and use models. The UTAUT model will be

utilized and developed to achieve this goal. However, in this study propensity to act has been added as moderating variables for overcoming the limitations of the UTAUT model.

Nowadays, individuals and organizations are using Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in order to accommodate our daily needs. Information and Communication Technology has become a useful tool in promoting the quality of education worldwide. Nevertheless, measurement of IT innovation of acceptance and behavioral intention to use has been largely ignored in the literature while information technology has broadly been confirmed as the indicators of success. The present research attempts to bridge this gap, by empirically assessing and comparing the perception of teachers towards acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in educational institutions. The results of this research are important for many reasons because of the implications of research should be used to take actions by the public policy decision-makers.

2. Background of the Study

A number of behavioral theories have been applied to examine the process of information technology acceptance by end-users. Some of which are Theory of Reason Action (TRA), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), Task-Technology Fit Theory (TTF), and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Amongst these theories, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was found as a model that has been widely used in various studies on the adoption process of information technology. Following these models, in 2003, Venkatesh and his colleagues developed a new model called Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). Its predictor variables are performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating condition. Lee and Runge (2001) concluded that the innovation possessed actual influence toward the adoption of an information system by institutions. Several IS adoption models have been developed and proposed to explain users' acceptance and use of Information Technology. Researchers used these IS adoption models to explain technology acceptance in different contexts such as e-learning (Cheng, 2012) and multimedia-based learning systems (Lee and Ryu, 2014).

Another accredited intentions based model is Shapero's (1982) Entrepreneurial Event (SEE) one that is somehow conceptually similar to the Ajzen's TPB. Based on the model, a decision maker should perceive feasibility (self-efficacy) and desirability (TPB's attitude and social norms) of the opportunity so as to have a propensity to act and become intent (Krueger, 2009). Both models of the TPB and SEE have gone tested empirically and presented a high

level of robustness (Krueger et al. 2000). According to Krueger (2009), “a comparative test found support for both models and post hoc analysis suggested that the optimal model would include the propensity to act from Shapero’s SEE model. Using Shapero’s terminology, Krueger and Brazeal’s (1994) entrepreneurial model emphasizes the constructs of propensity to act integrating in the conceptualization of these constructs. Considering the critical points rely on UTAUT alone to predict IT adoption behavior would be inappropriate. Moreover, there is a need to find variables that are able to capture the role of external factors that affect an individual’s decisions to accept and behavioral intention to use of IT. In this model precipitating events is a moderating variable which is able to capture the role of external factors and improve the intention-behavior gap. This model has the potential to mitigate the limitations of the UTAUT model and thus assist in providing a better understanding of IT acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in both districts education institution.

The final construct measured is BI to use IT innovation Services in education institutions, which is directly influenced by Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI) and, Facilitating Conditions (FC) with Propensity to Act (PA) additionally influencing the level of Behavioral Intention (BI), and Use Behavior (UB) these seven predictors form an Extended UTAUT model for predicting behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in education institutions.

3. Research Model Associated with Hypothesis Development

This paper used the UTAUT-model (Venkatesh et al, 2003) as a base model to empirically assessing and comparing the perception of teachers towards acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in educational institutions of two districts namely Barishal and Patuakhali under Barisal Education Board in Barishal division.

We considered performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions as determinants toward behavior intention to use of IT innovation services. Literature shows that previous experience with the information technology makes it easier for people to accept and they consider it as the key to success of the information technology. Therefore we consider propensity to act as moderating factors that influences the relationship between behavioral intentions and use behavior of IT innovation. *Figure-1* shows the research model.

Figure-1: Research Model

Although ICT offers an improved approach to providing IT innovation services, its acceptance by end users remains slow. Teachers are the traditionally homogeneous sample that challenges to the successful implementation of IT innovative services. The link between the intention and behavior is most likely influenced by a number of factors, some controllable, others uncontrollable; therefore, external factors are likely to play a significant role. With respect to the importance of information technology for an organization's success, a large and growing body of literature details IT adoption and use behavior, and several models have been developed to explain users' acceptance of technology (Koivumaki et al., 2008; Kannabiran, 2012). Pai and Huang (2011) indicated that PE affects BI to use of information technology.

Sun et al. (2013) suggest that EE has a strong influence on the users' intention to use information system acceptance. Lu et al., (2005) have found that SI has a strong impact on users' intention to adopt the technology. A study by Boontarig et al. (2012) suggested that FC positively influences the behavioral intention and use behavior of using IT-related innovation services. Yi et al. (2006) found that FC is a direct determinant of behavioral intention and use of technology.

Krueger et al., (2000) revealed that propensity to act as direct determinants of intention and find a significant and positive relationship between propensity to act and intention. Venkatesh (2000) empirically tested that BI explains the user's actual UB of technology. The relationship between the behavioral intention (BI) and actual use behavior (UB) is well documented in many research fields and that indicates BI is a valid predictor of actual UB (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Sheppard et al., 1988). Therefore, it is expected that the performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, propensity to act, will positively influence teacher's behavioral intention to use IT-related innovation in the educational institutions. The above discussion lead this study to posit the following hypothesis:

H₁: *PE will have a positive influence on the acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation Services*

H₂: *EE will have a positive influence on the acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation Services*

H₃: *SI will have a positive influence on the acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation Services*

H₄: *FC will have a positive influence on the acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation Services*

H₅: *FC will have a positive influence on the actual use of IT innovation Services*

H₆: *PA moderates positively the relationship between the teacher's Behavioral Intention (BI) and Use Behavior of IT innovation Services*

H₇: *BI will have a significant effect on the teacher's actual use of IS- innovations*

4. Methodology

4.1 Questionnaire Development Procedure

The present study develops a research framework to predict the level of acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT as well as assessing and comparing the teacher's perceptions towards acceptance and behavioral intention to use of Information Technology (IT) between Barishal and Patuakhali District's education institutions. The questions that measure propensity to Act (PA) were adopted from Krueger (1993), Krueger and Brazeal (1994), and Krueger, et al (2000). Some words were modified suit to the context of the study. Items that measure Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI), Facilitating Conditions (FC), Behavioral Intention (BI), and Use Behavior (UB) of IT innovation services were adapted from Venkatesh et al., (2003).

4.2 Data Collection Strategies

Questionnaires were designed to gather information about the constructs in the research model at the place of two districts (Barishal and Patuakhali) at Barisal division in Bangladesh. A Likert scale is appropriate when the research needs to measure the respondents' attitude toward constructs. Thus, the 5 points Likert type scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree) was built to gather the information. The questionnaires were

distributed based on probability sampling to the teacher who is involved in education service profession in education institutions. We chose only teachers of education institutions because of the most influential people affecting innovation and change in educational sector. A total of 450 questionnaires were sent to Barishal and Patuakhali districts education institutions, and 250 complete questionnaires were collected with a respondent rate of 55.55%.

4.3 Data Analysis Tools and Techniques

The obtained information was analyzed using the statistical software package SPSS version 22.0. This study tested the model using structural equation modeling using AMOS-23. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (version-22) software and its supplement AMOS (version-23) were found to be the appropriate and the most suitable tools for analyzing the quantitative data for this study. Statistical techniques of univariate analyses and bivariate were used. The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique was used to test a set of relationship between independents and a dependent variable. The relationships among all of the variables for the sample group were investigated through correlation analysis. The direct, indirect, and meditational effects of the study variables were tested using structural equation modeling procedures. The current study used two exploratory procedures viz., Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to identify the underlying data structure for each construct. Once an acceptable measurement model is available, the structural model evaluation should be able to start. A similar set of model fit indices was used to test the structural model.

5. Results of the Data Analysis and Discussions

The survey was completed by 204 respondents. These, 64.7% were males and 35.3% were females in the academic institutions. The following section will describe each group and provide the findings of the analysis.

5.1. Demographic Description of Respondents

The following table-2 provides a general overview of the teacher demographic information, such as age, gender, educational level, computer knowledge, and internet knowledge and use experience. The demographic characteristics of respondents presented in Figure-2 show those percentages who participated in the study.

5.1.1 Barishal

A simple random sampling was used to recruit participants. The study sample consisted who are fully or partially engaged in education institution at Barishal and Pauakhali Districts in Barishal Division. The participants (n=102) consisted of 70 (68.6%) were male and 32 (31.4%) were female. The majority, 45.1 percent of teacher respondents belonged to 20 to 40 years of age groups, 35.3 percent of them belonged to 41 to 50 years of age group and 19.6 percent of them were above 50 years of age. The sample displayed a different level of education: 58.8% (n=60) had master's degree from the different university, and 32.4% (n=33) had Bachelor degree and 4.9% (n=5) very few of respondents had a higher education degree. Mobile and Computer ((m & c) user experience, 37.3 percent of them had 4 to 6 years of user experience in their personal life and 30.4 percent of them had less than 4 years of experience and, 32.4 percent of them had more than 6 years use experience of mobile phone and computer or laptop in their daily life or in the workplace.

As table reveals, 34.3% (n=35) of the respondents had poor computer knowledge i.e. almost one-third of the respondents had little bit computer knowledge, 32.4% (n=33) of the respondents were from the moderate group, 20.6% (n=21) of the participants were good in computer knowledge while small percentage of about 12.7% (n=13) did have very good computer skills or experiences.

Figure-2: Demographic Information's of the respondents

5.1.2 Patuakhali

Respondents completed the survey, of which 62 (60.8%) were males and 40 (39.2%) were females. Also, the age distribution shows about 58.8% (n=60) respondents were aged 41 to 50 and the second group was aged 41 to 50 of 31.4% (n=32 %) and 10 (9.8%) of the percentage of the respondent who was older than 50 years. Respondent was asked to specify their education level. With regard to education, 50 (49%) had Master's Degree qualifications, 37 (36.3%) had bachelor degree program, higher education like Ph.D. holders were 10 (9.8%) with 83.3% of them having 1 to 6 years of mobile phone usage experience. As the table reveals, 41.2% (n=42) of the respondents were from the moderate group, almost 34.3 (n=35) of the respondents had little bit of computer knowledge, 15.7% (n=16) of the participants were good in computer knowledge while a small percentage of about 8.8% (n=9) did have very good computer skills or experiences.

Based on the above statistics, we can predict that more of the teachers and staffs are nowadays with the behavioral intention to engaging with information technology (IT) innovation services in their predefined workplace over time. Consequently, this result has a significant effect on technology acceptance decision and behavioral intention to use Information Technology (IT) innovation services in Barishal and Patuakhali district's education institutions.

5.2 Descriptive Results of the Teachers Perception towards Acceptance of IT

To measure the degree of acceptance and behavioral intention (BI) to use behavior (UB) of Information Technology (IT) in Barishal and Patuakhali districts education institutions, the scale developed by Venkatesh et al., (2003) and Krueger, et al (2000) was used. Their scale consists of 27 items; all of the items measure the construct of Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI), and Facilitating Conditions, Propensity to Act (PA), Use Behavior (UB), and Behavioral Intention (BI). Descriptive Results of Barishal and Patuakhali Education Institution's Teachers Perception to Level of Acceptance and Use of IT innovation services in their workplace are shown in table-1.

Items were rated on 5 point rating scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Higher the mean (4+) score measures the positive degree of acceptance of IT innovation and lowers the mean ($1 \leq 3.99$) score measures a low level of acceptance and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in education institutions either Barishal or Patuakhali districts. Considering the education institutions of Barishal District, responses of 22 items were averaged to measure acceptance and BI-UB of IT. 22-items Mean score of constructs of Barishal districts is higher than recommended value (i.e. $4.28 > 4$) it means

teachers of educational institutions in the Barisal district are strongly agree to accept and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in their job. On the other hand regarding Patuakhali district, table-1 reveals that mean score is higher than recommended value (i.e. $4.27 > 4$) it denotes teachers is strongly to use of IT innovation services in their respective educational institutions.

Code used CFA	Barishal						Patuakhali						
	SD	D	N	A	SD	Mean±S.D	SD	D	N	A	SD	Mean±S.D	
	(%)						(%)						
PE-1	--	--	32.4	17.6	50.0		4.17±0.89	--	7.80	34.3	15.7		42.2
PE-2	--	3.90	19.6	44.1	32.4	4.04±0.82	--	3.90	35.3	32.4	28.4	3.85±0.88	
PE-3	--	12.7	14.7	21.6	51.0	4.10±1.08	--	2.9	11.8	35.3	50.0	4.32±0.79	
PE-4	--	6.90	10.8	23.5	58.8	4.34±0.92	--	8.80	22.5	18.6	50.0	4.09±1.03	
EE-1	--	12.7	10.8	8.80	67.6	4.31±1.09	--	5.90	6.90	13.7	73.5	4.54±0.86	
EE-2	--	13.7	17.6	9.80	58.8	4.13±1.14	--	9.80	6.90	3.90	79.4	4.52±0.99	
EE-3	--	8.80	19.6	18.6	52.9	4.15±1.03	--	17.6	9.80	9.80	62.7	4.17±1.18	
EE-4	--	5.90	31.4	18.6	44.1	4.00±0.99	--	10.8	28.4	8.80	52.0	4.01±1.11	
SI-1	--	--	15.7	42.2	42.2	4.26±0.71	--	8.80	21.6	4.90	64.70	4.25±1.07	
SI-2	--	--	--	10.8	89.2	4.89±0.31	--	4.90	23.5	2.00	69.6	4.36±1.00	
SI-3	--	--	--	9.80	90.2	4.80±0.59	--	9.80	19.6	7.80	62.7	4.23±1.08	
SI-4	--	--	30.4	8.80	60.8	4.30±0.90	--	--	29.4	--	70.6	4.41±0.91	
FC-1	--	4.90	16.7	14.7	63.7	4.37±0.93	--	5.90	21.6	7.80	64.7	4.31±1.00	
FC-2	--	7.80	21.6	18.6	52.0	4.14±1.01	--	8.80	19.6	5.90	65.7	4.28±1.06	
FC-3	--	8.80	10.8	30.4	50.0	4.21±0.96	--	20.6	17.6	17.6	44.1	3.85±1.19	
FC-4	--	3.90	12.7	8.80	74.50	4.52±0.86	--	8.80	22.5	16.7	52.0	4.11±1.04	
PA-1	--	4.90	16.7	10.8	67.6	4.41±0.93	--	2.90	3.90	7.80	85.3	4.75±0.66	
PA-2	--	9.8	22.5	15.7	52.0	4.09±1.06	--	10.8	4.90	10.8	73.5	4.47±1.00	
PA-3	--	12.7	20.6	17.6	49.0	4.02±1.10	--	10.8	12.7	5.90	70.6	4.36±1.06	
PA-4	--	9.8	27.5	17.6	45.1	3.98±1.06	--	17.6	20.6	9.80	52.0	3.96±1.20	
BI-1	--	4.90	6.90	7.80	80.4	4.63±0.81	--	11.8	12.7	17.6	57.8	4.21±1.06	
BI-2	--	17.6	16.7	12.7	52.9	4.00±1.18	--	7.80	11.8	8.80	71.6	4.44±0.98	
BI-3	--	--	21.6	13.7	64.7	4.43±0.82	--	13.7	14.7	7.80	63.7	4.21±1.13	
BI-4	--	3.90	18.6	19.6	57.8	4.31±0.91	--	4.90	14.7	12.7	67.6	4.43±0.91	
UB-1	--	2.9	17.6	27.5	52.0	4.28±0.86	--	13.7	16.7	6.90	62.70	4.18±1.14	
UB-2	--	9.8	2.0	12.7	75.5	4.53±0.94	--	4.90	6.90	9.80	78.40	4.61±0.82	
UB-3	--	18.6	11.8	12.7	56.9	4.07±1.19	--	6.90	5.90	17.6	69.6	4.50±0.88	
Barishal: Teachers Perception to use of IT innovation service						4.28±0.93	Patuakhali: Teachers Perception to use of IT innovation service						4.27±1.00

Table-1: Descriptive Results of the Teachers Perception to Level of Acceptance and Use of IT innovation services in their workplace

5.3 Contrast between Barishal and Patuakhali Districts along with the Prevalence of Acceptance of IT Innovation Services in Educational Institutions

The contrast between Barishal and Patuakhali districts along with the prevalence of acceptance of IT innovation services in educational institutions is shown in table-2.

Significance construct is equaled to “District (Barishal&Patuakhali) Frequency value of education institution’s individual construct” minus “average value of constructs”; if it shows higher positive value it means the degree of acceptance of IT innovation in educational institutions is good enough in the context of ICT and, insignificant refers to Frequency value of education institution’s individual construct is less than average value, it shows always negative value in the outer column it means the teacher of the respective district did not accept or focus on the respective construct in context of ICT in the education sector.

Code Used in CFA	Barishal		Patuakhali		Differences		Ave. (n/7)	Barishal		Patuakhali	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	5= (1-3)	6= (2-4)		8= (1-7)	(9)	10= (3-7)	(11)
	Fre.	Per.	Fre.	Per.	Fre.	Per.					
PE	19	18.6	11	10.8	8	7.8	14.57	4.4	Sig.	-3.6	N.Sig
EE	18	17.6	13	12.7	5	4.9	14.57	3.4	Sig.	-1.6	N.Sig
SI	13	12.7	15	14.7	-2	-2	14.57	-1.6	N.Sig	0.4	Sig.
FC	12	11.8	16	15.7	-4	-3.9	14.57	-2.6	N.Sig	1.4	Sig.
PA	15	14.7	13	12.7	2	2	14.57	0.4	Sig.	-1.6	N.Sig.
BI	12	11.8	13	12.7	-1	-0.9	14.57	-2.6	N.Sig	-1.6	Sig.
UB	13	12.7	21	20.6	-8	-7.9	14.57	-1.6	N.Sig	6.4	Sig.
Total	102	100	102	100	0	0	102				

Table-2: Contrast between Barishal and Patuakhali districts along with the prevalence of acceptance of IT innovation services in educational institutions

According to the result of the measurement of the absolute deviation of two districts is good enough to accept and behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services in their respective districts. In this research, Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI), Facilitating Conditions (FC), Propensity to Act (PA), Behavioral Intention (BI) and Use Behavior (UB) is considered as the constructs of the model. Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE) and Propensity to Act (PA) among are higher than Patuakhali districts, on the other hand, Social Influence (SI), Facilitating Conditions (FC), and Behavioral Intention (BI) are comparatively better than Barishal District (see figure-3).

Figure-3: The measurement of the absolute deviation of two districts IT innovation construct. The above figure reveals that academic institutions teachers both in Barishal and in Patuakhali have a positive intention to use information technology in their jobs. The majority of the teachers 85.6% or, $(4.28 \times 100/5)$ in Barishal and 85.4% or, $(4.27 \times 100/5)$ in Patuakhali districts answered that they consider behavioral intention to use of information technology. In this study, we assessed through regarding questions that the teacher's negative perceptions of behavioral intention to use of information technology in academic institutions show that 4.57% $[(0.93 \times 102)/5 - (100 - 85.6)]$ teachers of Barishal district and 5.8% $[(1.00 \times 102)/5 - (100 - 85.4)]$ teachers of Patuakhali district consider that it is more difficult to create perception of acceptance and behavioral intention to use of information technology in academic institutions. Based on the statistical outcome of study area it is interestingly noted that actual difference between Barishal and Patuakhali districts education institutions teachers' negative behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services is very few percentage 1.23% among the teachers.

Barishal district's teacher is more progressive to accept the IT innovation rather than Patuakhali district's education institutions teachers. In this sense, both Barishal and Patuakhali districts education institutions teacher's attitudes toward behavioral intention to use show a favorable perception and high degree to uses of information technology in their jobs. There exists a significant effect of information technology on the education institutions among the teachers of both districts namely Barishal and Patuakhali. It is interesting to note that the same attributes were placed in the study area (Study-1 & 2) by both samples with no significant differences between the means and standard deviation in the educational institutions. This shows that the teacher's perceptions are quite homogeneous in the two

different samples in Study area-1 (Barishal) and Study area-2 (Patuakhali) districts at the Barisal division in Bangladesh.

Figure-3: Actual difference between two district’s positive behavioral intention and negative behavioral intention to use of IT innovation in the educational institutions.

5.4 Convergent Validity

In the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), convergent validity relies on the average variance extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) as a base. CFA of the Barishal district’s depicted that all composite reliabilities are above 0.79. In addition, it shows also, that the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is above 0.67. The table shows that the estimated constructs loading ranged from 0.77 to 0.99 and AVE ranged from 0.67 to 0.78 and CR ranged from 0.79 to 0.93 are greater than the recommended levels. Since the factor loadings, composite reliabilities and average variance extracted of the construct are at acceptable levels in the educations institutions of the Barishal district. CFA of the Patuakhali district’s depicted that all composite reliabilities are above 0.90. In addition, it shows also, that the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is above 0.68. The table shows that the estimated constructs loading ranged from 0.71 to 0.98 and AVE ranged from 0.68 to 0.76 and CR ranged from 0.90 to 0.92 are greater than the recommended levels. Since the factor loadings, composite reliabilities and average variance extracted of the construct are at acceptable levels in the educations institutions of the Patuakhali district.

Construct	Items Code	Loading		AVE		Δ	CR		Δ
		Barishal	Patuakhali	Bari.	Patua.		Bari.	Patua.	
Performance Expectancy (PE)	PF-1	0.80	0.86	0.77	0.73	0.04	0.93	0.91	0.02
	PF-2	0.92	0.84						
	PF-3	0.80	0.87						
	PF-4	0.99	0.86						
Effort Expectancy (EE)	EE-1	0.81	0.81	0.67	0.73	-0.06	0.89	0.92	-0.03
	EE-2	0.86	0.91						
	EE-3	0.86	0.80						
	EE-4	0.76	0.90						
Social Influence (SI)	SI-1	0.88	0.83	0.69	0.70	-0.01	0.90	0.90	0.00
	SI-2	0.77	0.82						
	SI-3	0.87	0.84						
	SI-4	0.80	0.86						
Facilitating Conditions (FC)	FC-1	0.86	0.82	0.73	0.73	0.00	0.91	0.92	-0.01
	FC-2	0.93	0.96						
	FC-3	0.83	0.87						
	FC-4	0.78	0.79						
Propensity to Act (PA)	PA-1	0.84	0.92	0.75	0.68	0.07	0.92	0.90	0.02
	PA-2	0.88	0.81						
	PA-3	0.85	0.79						
	PA-4	0.90	0.78						
Behavioral Intention (BI)	BI-1	0.92	0.71	0.78	0.75	0.03	0.93	0.92	0.01
	BI-2	0.80	0.98						
	BI-3	0.99	0.88						
	BI-4	0.81	0.87						
Use Behavior (UB)	UB-1	0.86	0.91	0.74	0.76	-0.02	0.79	0.90	0.00
	UB-2	0.83	0.80						
	UB-3	0.89	0.90						

Table-3: Convergent Validity for the Constructs of Barishal and Patuakhali Districts

5.5 Discriminant Validity

In this study, when the correlations are lower than the square root of the average variance extracted by a construct, constructs are said to have discriminant validity. As shown in the table, all squares roots of the AVEs are higher than the correlations between constructs and that definitely confirms adequately discriminant validity. The results shown in Table-6 reveals that all constructs in this study confirm the discriminant validity of the data of both selected districts.

Cons.	Barishal							Patuakhali						
	PF	EE	SI	FC	PA	BI	UB	PF	EE	SI	FC	PA	BI	UB
PE	0.88	0.63	0.71	0.72	0.56	0.66	0.62	0.85						
EE		0.82	0.74	0.69	0.73	0.72	0.74	0.68	0.85					
SI			0.83	0.52	0.61	0.70	0.76	0.69	0.78	0.83				
FC				0.85	0.69	0.67	0.71	0.76	0.67	0.77	0.85			
PA					0.87	0.60	0.72	0.69	0.78	0.71	0.70	0.82		
BI						0.88	0.72	0.78	0.77	0.65	0.61	0.64	0.87	
UB							0.86	0.68	0.64	0.60	0.71	0.58	0.56	0.87

Table-4: Discriminant Validity Results for the Measurement Model

5.6 The Model fit indices

The goodness-of-fit indices (shown in Table) were all good for the total sample of Barishal and Patuakhali districts. The final fit for the first model (Model-A for Barishal) in the calibration sample shows a fairly good fit with the data collected, with CFI = 0.92, GFI= 0.91, TLI = 0.98, IFI = 0.94, NFI = 0.93, NNFI = 0.92, SRMR = 0.093, RMSEA = 0.084, and CMIN/DF= 4.20. The final fit for the second model (Model-B for Patuakhali) shows that the model achieved a good level of fit, $\chi^2 = 282.583$, $\chi^2 / df = 4.77$, CFI = 0.90, GFI= 0.93, TLI = 0.95, IFI = 0.95, NFI = 0.91, NNFI = 0.90, SRMR = 0.098, RMSEA = 0.078. The model presents the possibility of factors influencing technology acceptance and behavioral intention to use of Information Technology (IT) Services in education institution of both districts namely Barishal and Patuakhali.

Fit Indices of the Model											
Sample	X ²	df	X ² /df	CFI	GFI	TLI	IFI	NFI	NNFI	SRMR	RMSEA
Model-A	1193.07	284	4.20	0.92	0.91	0.98	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.093	0.084
Model-B	1356.32	284	4.77	0.90	0.93	0.95	0.95	0.91	0.90	0.098	0.078

Table-5: Model fit indices

5.7 Testing the Hypotheses on Behavioral Intention (BI) to Use of IT innovation services

According to the findings in the table-8 the hypotheses of Barisal district perspective on Behaviour Intention, testing the relationship between the constructs and the behavioral intention to use of IT, regarding to the Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI), Facilitating Conditions (FC), Propensity to Act (PA) on the behavior intention (BI), Hypothesis **H₁**, **H₂**, **H₃**, **H₄**, **H₅** and **H₆** was supported. Finally, Behavior intention will have a significant effect on the actual use ($p < 0.001$) of IS services in their predefined jobs over time, therefore **H₇** was supported. Patuakhali district perspective on behavior intention to use of IT the results shows that the relationships among PE & BI, EE & BI, SI & BI, FC & BI, PA & BI, BI & UB were significant. Therefore, **H₁**, **H₂**, **H₃**, **H₄**, **H₅**, **H₆** and **H₇** were accepted in the current study.

Hyp.	Relationship	Sig. level	Barishal				Patuakhali			
			C.R	Beta	Sig.	Sup.	C.R	Beta	Sig.	Sup
H₁	PE and BI	P<0.05	6.80	0.25	P<0.05	Yes	5.60	0.32	P<0.05	Yes
H₂	EE and BI	P<0.05	6.95	0.56	P<0.05	Yes	8.98	0.44	P<0.05	Yes
H₃	SI and BI	P<0.05	7.77	0.38	P<0.05	Yes	4.76	0.23	P<0.05	Yes
H₄	FC and BI	P<0.05	8.87	0.37	P<0.05	Yes	7.54	0.48	P<0.05	Yes
H₅	PA and BI	P<0.05	4.54	0.68	P<0.05	Yes	5.65	0.56	P<0.05	Yes
H₆	PA and UB	P<0.05	5.87	0.18	P<0.05	Yes	8.37	0.39	P<0.05	Yes
H₇	BI and UB	P<0.05	7.87	0.46	P<0.05	Yes	6.27	0.34	P<0.05	Yes

Table-6: Testing the Hypotheses on Behavioral Intention (BI) to Use of IT innovation services

6. Conclusions

The findings reveals that the Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI), and Facilitating Conditions, Propensity to Act (PA), Use Behavior (UB), and Behavioral Intention (BI) construct in the information technology acceptance decision is positively predicted and the significant in the perspective of education institutions. Based on statistics, Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE) and Propensity to Act (PA) have a significant impact on the degree of acceptance towards behavioral intention to use of IT innovation and other remaining four constructs namely Social Influence (SI), and Facilitating Conditions, Behavioral Intention (BI) and, Use Behavior (UB) do not have an impact on BI-US of IT i.e. insignificant constructs to education institutions in Barishal district. On the other side regarding Patuakhali district's education institutions constructs; Social Influence (SI), and Facilitating Conditions, Behavioral Intention (BI) and, Use Behavior (UB) have a significant impact on the degree of acceptance towards behavioral intention to use of IT innovation and other remaining three construct Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE) and Propensity to Act (PA) do not have an impact on BI-US of IT i.e. insignificant constructs for education institutions in Patuakhali district. Based on the above statistics, we can predict that more of the teachers are nowadays engaging with information technology (IT) innovation services in their predefined workplace over time. Consequently, this result has a significant effect on technology acceptance decision and behavioral intention to use Information Technology (IT) innovation services in Barishal and Patuakhali district's education institutions. The estimated parameters were all statistically significant between the latent and measured variables.

7. Implications for Policy Guidelines

The current study revised and validated the UTAUT model in a new culture and context. The results show that the model is a robust model, to measure behavioral intention to use of information technology in academic institutions. The results of this study confirm the applicability of the UTAUT model to measure the teacher's perceptions towards technology acceptance and behavioral intention to use Information Technology (IT) innovations in education institutions. Adding, propensity to act made the model more powerful to test different perspectives of technology acceptance. From the methodological perspective, this study offers important insights into analyzing acceptance behavior. This study introduces an approach to measure the perception of teacher's behavioral intention to use of information technology innovation services. There is a lack of a conceptual approach in technology acceptance modeling. The study was conducted only for measuring the teacher's perceptions

of behavioral intention to use of information technology innovation services in educational institutions.

Overall findings of this work significantly enhance our understanding of teacher's perception towards behavioral intention to use of information technology. The Barishal Education Board under Bangladesh Education Ministry may also use this framework to diagnose causes for the reluctance of use of IS innovation by teachers and, policymakers could facilitate and provide guidance in relation to the acceptance and usage of IT innovation in the educational institutions.

8. Limitations and Further Research Direction

Some limitations of this study should be addressed. Limitation of this study is to teachers are traditionally homogeneous population segment. In this study, we select the homogeneous sample of the population and used these data for analyzing and interpreting to assessing the behavioral intention to use of IT innovation services between two district's education institutions. To address this study, future studies could examine eight divisional populations as a whole and obtained a more diverse sample from different districts as a way of evaluating the IT innovation services.

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